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School Leaders' Promotion of Mental Health: A Comparative Study

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Abstract

The present study aimed to explore the implementation of health promotion (HP) in schools in Malaysia and Switzerland, investigate how school leaders' attitudes are related to such efforts, and identify contextual factors that contribute to HP implementation. School leaders from both countries (Malaysia and Switzerland) completed an online survey including the School Promotion of Social and Emotional Health, and a comparative analysis (hierarchical regression analysis) was conducted to investigate the levels of HP implementation in both countries and the possible effects of school leaders' attitudes. Although both countries had comparable results on overall HP implementation levels, Malaysia had higher levels for certain subscales, such as fostering a positive school community. In Switzerland, HP implementation was closely linked to school leaders' attitudes. Possible explanations for these findings can be found in the distinct governing systems of the two countries. This study offers a unique comparative perspective on HP in two countries with distinctly different governing structures. It also contributes to educational policy by highlighting the need for context-sensitive approaches to HP implementation.

Introduction

Recent years have seen an increase in the prevalence of mental health needs among children and adolescents worldwide (Kieling et al., 2024; Lu et al., 2024). This highlights the need for setting-based, whole-school health promotion (HP) approaches that integrate early detection, prevention, and social-emotional skill development into everyday school life (Barbieri et al., 2022). International frameworks, such as the Global Standards for Health-Promoting Schools, emphasize this need and promote system-level strategies for transforming mental health (OECD, 2023, 2025; World Health Organization (WHO) and UNESCO, 2021).

The WHO's holistic approach to HP emphasizes structural and cultural transformation across the school system and coordinated engagement at all institutional levels

(Nielsen et al., 2015; WHO Expert Committee, 1997). This means, HP implementation requires aligned actions across curricula, the school's social and physical environments, and health

services. In this context, implementation can be understood as a set of activities aimed at putting a practice or program into action (Fixsen et al., 2005).

School leaders function as gatekeepers, enabling or constraining HP implementation (Dadaczynski and Hering, 2021; Samdal and Rowling, 2015). They sustain motivation, coordinate organizational processes, and ensure HP's integration in schools (Dadaczynski and Paulus, 2015; Skott, 2021). Despite their significant role in HP, few studies have examined how school leaders handle this responsibility (Adams et al., 2023; Dadaczynski et al., 2022).

School leaders operate within expectations set by educational authorities and legal mandates. Their work is shaped by economic, political, and sociocultural contexts (Hallinger, 2018), as well as by institutional structures influencing time spent on leadership, administration, and community engagement (Lee and Hallinger, 2012). Comparative studies are crucial to understand how governing and institutional settings shape school leadership practices (Harris and Jones, 2015; Huber, 2004; Johnson et al., 2008).

Although HP has become an increasingly important responsibility for school leaders, studies examining the relationship between institutional structures and school leaders' HP activities are scarce. Moreover, research on holistic HP approaches and HP implementation in middle-income countries (Levinson et al., 2019) remains limited. The present study addressed these gaps by comparing HP implementation and school leaders' attitudes in Malaysia and Switzerland. Comparing a high-income, decentralized Western system (Switzerland) with a middle-income, centralized Southeast Asian system (Malaysia) allows broader theoretical insights into the interplay between governing structures and school leadership in promoting health (Green, 2003).

Both countries face increasing challenges related to youth mental and social health (Ambrosetti et al., 2021; Liu and Kuai, 2025; Mat Rifin et al., 2025) but operate within fundamentally different governing structures, representing theoretically valuable contrasts. This study also aimed to identify HP implementation variations arising from contextual disparities and differences in school leader attributes. Malaysia has a centralized education system, HP oversight lies with the Ministry of Education Malaysia (2013) and the State Education Department, ensures a clear, uniform structure (Adams, 2023; UNESCO, 2014). Switzerland, a high-income Western country, has a federal decentralized educational system that grants school leaders significant autonomy with cantonal and municipal authorities overseeing quality control (Hangartner and Heinzer, 2016; Hangartner and Svaton, 2013; Huber, 2011). These governing systems shape how school leaders prioritize and enact HP initiatives, influencing their professional judgment and local adaption (Nordholm et al., 2025).

To gain a deeper understanding of the contextual and institutional mechanisms affecting HP practices and leadership commitments, this study addressed the following research questions (RQs):

- RQ1: What similarities and differences in the perceptions of school leaders in Malaysia and Switzerland regarding HP implementation levels can be identified, and how are these perceptions related to school characteristics (i.e., students' socioeconomic status (SES), school level, and school size)?
- RQ2: How are school leaders' attitudes related to HP implementation levels?

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. First, it provides an overview of the relevant literature. Then, it outlines the methodology and presents the results. Finally, it discusses the findings, addresses the study's limitations, and offers concluding remarks.

Previous Research

This section explores international research on school-based HP and the role of school leaders, especially in Switzerland, other German-speaking countries, and Malaysia.

HP in Schools

International research has yielded mixed results on the extent of holistic HP implementation in schools and the factors influencing HP adoption (Dadaczynski and Hering, 2021; Hung et al., 2014; Samdal and Rowling, 2011). Larger schools may have more resources (Curless and Burns, 2003; Darlington et al., 2018; Hung et al., 2014), while smaller schools may better manage multilevel strategies (Cleary and English, 2005). Dadaczynski and Hering (2021) showed that primary schools in Germany often prioritize health more than secondary schools. Zumbrunn et al. (2016) found that primary schools in Switzerland concentrated on physical activity and nutrition, while secondary schools focused on substance abuse and mental health. Other studies have found that HP is especially important for students with a low SES, but schools with many of these students face greater HP-related challenges due to limited resources (e.g., Cronholm et al., 2015; Darlington et al., 2018).

Kunz Heim and Mittag (2016) surveyed teachers and found that HP measures were only partially implemented. Additionally, violence prevention was the most common, followed by physical activity, relaxation, psychosocial health, and addiction prevention.

Malaysian studies have examined factors that improve HP effectiveness. According to Gunasekaran et al. (2018), effective obesity management in schools requires the at-home support of families. Teo et al. (2019) found that knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to healthy eating are best targeted by providing schoolchildren with a healthy nutrition-enabling environment.

In summary, HP implementation varies widely depending on school size and level and the socioeconomic context. The studies in German-speaking countries revealed considerable variation in the topics addressed and the HP implementation levels. The influencing factors included the school level and students' SES. The studies in Malaysia primarily focused on physical health, and family

support and the school environment were key influencing factors. Notably, no studies have examined mental HP or systematically assessed HP implementation levels. This knowledge gap is compounded by a lack of adequate, reliable measurement tools, making it difficult to determine the extent and quality of HP implementation (Dix et al., 2019).

School Leaders and HP

School leaders are pivotal contributors to HP activities (Samdal and Rowling, 2011). Their influence extends across strategic planning, resource allocation, policy implementation, professional development, community engagement, and the fostering of supportive school environments (Dadaczynski et al., 2022; Hudson et al., 2020; Hung et al., 2014; Leksy et al., 2024; Samdal and Rowling, 2015). Moreover, their positions within structural, cultural, and institutional contexts and their attitudes toward HP can shape their interpretation and implementation of HP. For example, by setting health-related priorities and securing resources, they can ensure HP's integration into core school activities (Roberts et al., 2016). Health promoting leadership has been associated with better student health outcomes because leaders who prioritize HP can significantly enhance the school community's overall well-being (Dadaczynski et al., 2020; Velarde et al., 2022).

Adams et al. (2023) identified seven school leadership-related factors that impact HP implementation. One factor, school leaders' attitudes toward HP, was particularly influential. Samdal and Rowling (2011) demonstrated that, when school leaders prioritize health, they establish HP policies and actively promote and uphold them, significantly enhancing health initiatives' effectiveness. Tjomsland et al. (2009) found that, in Norway, school leaders' attitudes and commitment were key factors in HP implementation and sustainability. Clarke et al. (2015) showed that UK school leaders' primary motivation was a moral obligation to implement HP. Liu et al. (2019) showed that, in Taiwan, school leaders' willingness to sustain HP was associated with higher implementation levels. In Germany, Dadaczynski et al. (2020) found a significant relationship between school leaders' attitudes toward HP and implementation levels. The authors (2022) observed that the health literacy of school leaders in Switzerland only had a positive effect on HP implementation when they also had positive attitudes toward HP. Benoliel and Schechter (2023) and Skott (2021) highlighted the importance of aligning school leaders' interpretations of broader educational goals with those of actors across the multilevel education system to ensure successful HP implementation and school improvement in general.

Research Design and Methods

The study employed a cross-sectional quantitative survey design, a widely used approach for examining relationships among variables at a single timepoint (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Cross-

country comparisons and international research collaborations have long been recognized as critical for investigating the effectiveness of HP implementation in systems with different governing mechanisms and institutional arrangements (Hopp, 1990; Young et al., 2013).

Data were obtained from a June 2021 survey administered using Unipark (2023), an online survey provider specializing in scientific research solutions. The survey was part of a comparative study of school HP, which was funded by ETH Zurich's Bilateral Science and Technology Cooperation Programme with Asia. Building on established scales, a questionnaire was developed in English and translated into Malay and three of Switzerland's four national languages: German, French, and Italian. Participants were recruited using a convenience sampling approach targeting primary, secondary, and vocational school leaders. Survey links were distributed¹ and promoted through social media in Switzerland and emailed to all school leaders in Selangor and Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. In both countries, invitations were extended to school leadership team members, including principals and other school board members. This approach ensured that respondents had direct responsibility for school leadership and HP implementation, enabling informed insights into leadership practices and decision-making processes.

Several ethical considerations guided the survey's design and administration: The questionnaire was intentionally kept concise to minimize participant burden during the COVID-19 pandemic (Döring, 2023). Participation was voluntary, and respondents were able to withdraw from the survey at any time without negative consequences. To protect confidentiality and ensure data security, the survey was administered via a secure online platform no personal identifiers were collected, and all data were stored and managed in accordance with relevant data protection and privacy regulations.

Sample Characteristics

The data collected from the 1,058 respondents required extensive cleanup (i.e., excluding speeders and incomplete responses). The final sample consisted of 968 school leaders. Table I shows the sample characteristics and differences between the characterizing variables for Malaysia and Switzerland.

¹ The survey was distributed through school leader association newsletters in Switzerland's German-, French-, and Italian-speaking areas (Verband Schulleiterinnen und Schulleiter (VSLCH) and Conférence latine des chefs d'établissements de la scolarité obligatoire (CLACESO)) and the Schwyz University of Teacher Education newsletter.

Table I. School Leader Sample Characteristics and Differences Between Malaysia and Switzerland

		Total (<i>n</i> = 968)	Malaysia (<i>n</i> = 603)	Switzerland (<i>n</i> = 365)	Differences
Female	% (<i>n</i>)	63.2 (612)	73.9 (452)	43.8 (160)	Chi2(1) = 94.72 <i>p</i> < .001
Age (years)	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	47.2 (8.8)	45.27 (8.8)	50.39 (7.7)	<i>t</i> = 9.12 (966) <i>p</i> < .001
Organizational tenure (years)	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	5.74 (4.9)	4.71 (3.9)	7.44 (5.8)	<i>t</i> = 8.79 (966) <i>p</i> < .001
Primary school	% (<i>n</i>)	49.5 (479)	54.9 (331)	40.5 (148)	Chi2(1) = 18.72 <i>p</i> < .001
School size (number of students)	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	776 (556.4)	849 (509.5)	658 (608.5)	<i>t</i> = -5.26 (966) <i>p</i> < .001
Percentage of students with a low SES	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	34.96 (21.2)	39.69 (21.8)	27.14 (17.6)	<i>t</i> = -9.31 (966) <i>p</i> < .001

Note. *M* = mean, *SD* = standard deviation.

Measures

We used Dix *et al.*'s (2019) Survey of School Promotion of Social and Emotional Health (SSPESH) to measure the main outcome variable: the HP implementation level regarding mental health. The application of this scale in Switzerland and Malaysia is exploratory, as it has not previously been used outside its country of origin, Australia. Nevertheless, the authors note that, since the scale is grounded in the WHO's holistic Health Promoting Schools framework, it is suitable for use in international contexts (Dix *et al.*, 2019).

School leaders were asked to rate 13 statements regarding school practices on HP implementation on a four-point Likert scale (0 = not yet in place, 1 = introducing, 2 = taking hold, 3 = completely in place). SSPESH consists of four subscales: (1) Positive school community (4 items, e.g., *There is an effective leadership team in our school that is responsible for students' mental health and wellbeing.*). Its internal consistency was considered acceptable or good, with Cronbach's alpha values of .73 and .83 for Switzerland and Malaysia, respectively. (2) Student social and emotional learning (2 items, e.g., *Our whole school staff participates in opportunities to discuss students' development and the challenges they face.*). Its internal consistency ranged from questionable to acceptable (Switzerland: $\alpha = .64$, Malaysia: $\alpha = .77$). (3) Engaging families (3 items, e.g., *Activities for families that promote school-wide mental health and wellbeing are regularly offered.*). Its internal consistency was considered questionable or acceptable (Switzerland: $\alpha = .61$, Malaysia: $\alpha = .72$). (4) supporting students experiencing difficulties (4 Items, e.g., *Our school has clear referral pathways with local mental health services and supports families in accessing these services.*). Its internal consistency ranged from questionable to acceptable (Switzerland: $\alpha = .68$, Malaysia: $\alpha = .83$). In line with the formative nature of the applied scales, We expected to observe values in this range because formative

models do not anticipate high inter-item correlations (White et al., 2024). Across all 13 items, internal consistency was considered good (Switzerland = .84, Malaysia = .91).

As exploratory variable, school leaders' attitudes toward HP, was included in the present study and operationalized using Dadaczynski *et al.*'s (2020) six-item instrument (e.g., *The health of my staff and my students is very important to me.*), which had a five-point Likert scale (1 = agree completely, 5 = do not agree at all). Internal consistency was lower in Swiss participants ($\alpha = .63$) than Malaysian ones ($\alpha = .81$).

Analyses

We used SPSS version 28.0 for the statistical analyses. Initial checks for outliers were performed by creating box plot diagrams that revealed a few outliers. Univariate analyses were conducted to calculate measures such as the mean (M) and the standard deviation (SD). Difference tests (i.e., t-test, Chi2) were used to identify differences between the countries' main characteristics. Variables with significant differences were used as exploratory variables in subsequent analyses (Table I) to ensure that any differences were not due to differences in school-related factors.

To identify country-level differences in HP implementation levels, we ran a one-way between-groups multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) with the four subscales as dependent variables under the control of characteristics that differed between the countries. We then conducted a hierarchical regression analysis with HP implementation as the dependent variable. After standardizing all continuous independent variables (Aiken and West, 1991), we entered variables for school leader and school characteristics (i.e., school leaders' gender, age, and organizational tenure; school size and level; and students' low SES) in the first step (Model 1) and the main effects of school leaders' attitudes and countries in the second step (Model 2). In the third step, we entered the interaction term (country x school leaders' attitudes) (Model 3). We also conducted a simple slope analysis and visualized the moderation effect using the PROCESS tool for SPSS to interpret the interaction effect.

Results

Figure 1 shows that the overall HP implementation levels (total scale values) perceived by Malaysian and Swiss school leaders were similar (Malaysia: $M = 1.50$, $SD = .56$; Switzerland: $M = 1.45$, $SD = .60$). The MANOVA analysis showed that Malaysian school leaders had statistically significant higher results for three subscales: positive school community ($F(1, 964) = 41.34$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .041$), student social and emotional learning ($F(1, 964) = 63.24$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .062$), and engaging families ($F(1, 964) = 119.51$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .111$). Swiss school leaders only had significantly higher results for supporting students experiencing difficulties ($F(1, 964) = 32.72$, $p <$

.001, partial $\eta^2 = .033$). The attitudes toward HP were similar across the countries (Malaysia: $M = 4.73$, $SD = 0.35$; Switzerland: $M = 4.69$, $SD = .30$).

Figure 1. HP Implementation Levels per Subscale in Malaysia and Switzerland

Table II shows the stepwise regression analysis results. In Model 1, school size and level and SES were significant predictors of HP implementation. School leaders from larger schools had higher implementation levels ($b = 0.09$, $t(960) = 2.68$, $p < 0.01$), as did those from secondary schools ($b = 0.10$, $t(960) = 3.00$, $p < 0.01$). Implementation was lower in schools with a high percentage of students with a low SES ($b = -0.08$, $t(960) = -2.35$, $p < 0.05$). School leaders with positive attitudes toward HP ($b = 0.11$, $t(960) = 3.58$, $p < 0.01$) reported higher HP implementation levels. Collectively, these factors explained 4% of the variance in HP implementation ($R^2 = .037$ ($F(7, 960) = 6.30$, $p < 0.001$).

Adding country as an independent variable in Model 2 significantly increased the explained variance ($R^2 = 0.044$ ($F(8, 959) = 6.60$, $p < 0.001$; $\Delta R^2 = 0.008$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that “country” contributed to the HP implementation prediction. Malaysian school leaders reported slightly higher HP implementation levels than Swiss school leaders ($b = 0.11$ $t(959) = 2.90$, $p < 0.01$). In Model 3, the interaction effect was included. The main effect of attitudes toward HP remained significant, and the interaction effect between country and attitudes toward HP became significant ($b = -0.16$, $t(958) = -2.71$, $p < 0.01$). These effects indicate that school leaders’ attitudes play different roles in Malaysia and Switzerland.

Table II. Regression Analysis Results (Dependent Variable: HP Implementation)

Predictor	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Constant (SE)	.444 (0.28)	.390(0.28)	-.645 (0.47)
Gender	-0.015	-0.040	-0.043
Age	.004	0.026	0.023
Organizational tenure	0.065	0.082***	0.084*
School size	0.086**	0.059	0.054
School level	0.098**	0.111***	0.112***
Low SES	-0.075*	-0.104**	-0.105**
Attitudes	0.113***	0.108***	0.238***
Country		0.110**	0.109**
Country x Attitudes			-0.155**
R ² corrected	0.037	0.044	0.051
F	6.30 ***	6.60 ***	6.72 ***
(df1/df2)	(7/960)	(8/959)	(9/958)

Note. Multiple linear regression analysis (enter method), standardized β -coefficients, SE = standard error, R² = multiple determination coefficient

* = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.01$, *** = $p < 0.001$, two-tailed tests

Figure 2. Simple Slope Analysis (Dependent Variable: HP Implementation)

The simple slope analysis (Figure 2) revealed that Swiss school leaders' attitudes toward HP were positively and significantly related to HP implementation ($\beta = 0.41$, $SE = 0.010$, $p < 0.001$). However, no significant relationship was observed for Malaysian school leaders ($\beta = 0.09$, $SE = 0.07$, $p = 0.168$).

Discussion

Regarding RQ1, the findings revealed both similarities and differences between Malaysia and Switzerland. As the SSPESH had previously been applied only within the Australian context, the

present study extends its use to two additional national contexts, demonstrating the instrument's utility for assessing school health promotion implementation and supporting its application in cross-national comparative research. However, the absence of established reference values outside Australia limited direct comparisons, and the observed scores were lower than those reported by Dix et al. (2019). These differences are likely attributable to contextual variations, as the instrument was originally developed and validated within the Australian educational and policy framework, highlighting the need to consider national context when interpreting SSPESH scores and underscoring the present study's contribution to advancing the instrument's broader applicability and interpretability. Overall SSPESH scores were similar for Malaysian and Swiss school leaders, with HP implementation ranging from emerging to not yet established. At the subscale level, Malaysian school leaders reported higher implementation on the first three subscales, while Swiss school leaders reported higher levels on the fourth. In Malaysia, the centralized school governing system clearly defines HP responsibilities, with dedicated health teams implementing initiatives under guidance from the State Education Department and the Ministry of Education. The Malaysia Education Blueprint 2013–2025 emphasizes holistic development, including physical, mental, and emotional health (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2013). In Switzerland, mental HP plays a smaller role than academic performance, leaving prioritization to school leaders, while networks and agencies such as Schulnetz21, Gesundheitsförderung Schweiz, Radix, and the bildung und gesundheit Netzwerk Schweiz provide support (Hascher and Hagenauer, 2011).

The association between a higher percentage of students with low SES and lower HP implementation aligns with Darlington et al. (2018) and highlights the importance of addressing school resource disparities (Cronholm et al., 2015). Secondary schools showed higher HP implementation levels than primary schools, consistent with Zumbrunn et al. (2016) while school size was not significantly associated with implementation levels.

Regarding RQ2, school leaders' attitudes influenced HP implementation levels only in Switzerland. Swiss school leaders with more positive attitudes toward HP tended to report higher HP implementation levels. In Malaysia, by contrast, the stronger institutionalization of HP (e.g., well-defined guidelines, designated health teams) may render implementation less dependent on individual leaders' attitudes.

This pattern indicates that the influence of school leaders' attitudes is contingent on the degree of institutionalization within the school system. While prior studies show that positive attitudes among school leaders support the integration of HP into core school activities (Roberts et al., 2016; Tjomsland et al., 2009), our findings refine this understanding by demonstrating that such attitudinal effects are not universal and occur primarily in contexts with weaker institutionalization, where implementation depends more on local leadership.

Contribution to the Existing HP Knowledge Base

Although HP implementation differences between Malaysia and Switzerland were not particularly pronounced, distinct factors appeared to shape HP implementation, especially regarding the influence of Swiss school leaders' attitudes.

Variations in Governing Mechanisms and Institutional Arrangements Shape School Leaders' Capacity to Coordinate and Sustain HP Initiatives

Although the data did not allow for clear linear conclusions, they raised important questions about how governing systems might influence HP implementation. The Health-Promoting Schools philosophy emphasizes autonomy and active participation as core principles (Samdal and Rowling, 2015), and several studies highlight the importance of bottom-up approaches for sustainable, context-sensitive HP implementation (e.g. Durlak and DuPre, 2008; Madsen et al., 2016). However, other research suggests that centralized governance can help schools set priorities and achieve stronger HP outcomes (Hung et al., 2014; McIsaac et al., 2017), while excessive decentralization and weak guidance may hinder progress (Simovska et al., 2016). Given these mixed findings and the present study's results, it remains unclear which type of governing system best supports HP implementation. Future research should therefore examine how different governing mechanisms and institutional arrangements shape the development and sustainability of HP practices.

School Leadership and HP Implementation

The distinct implementation levels in Malaysia and Switzerland and the influence of attitudes can also be explained by the countries' school leadership models. Malaysia's interdisciplinary leadership structure may contribute to higher levels of implementation because distributing responsibility across professionals with diverse expertise helps HP be integrated into core school practices rather than treated as a peripheral activity. This distributed leadership model enhances professionalization and fosters cross-disciplinary collaboration, enabling schools to address HP implementation challenges more effectively (Roberts et al., 2016; Skott et al., 2021). In fact, Adams et al. (2023) underscored the vital role of shared responsibility in HP implementation.

In Switzerland, priority-setting and decision-making are left to school leaders, who must balance HP with a range of other responsibilities. The broad scope of their duties makes their role particularly complex and demanding. As a result, HP is rarely prioritized unless school leaders personally recognize its importance and value. Consequently, HP initiatives in Swiss schools tend to be implemented selectively, depending on school leaders' attitudes, available resources, and perceived relevance to the local context.

Limitations

Several study limitations should be acknowledged. First, its cross-sectional design limited the use of causal inferences. Second, the study's limited factors examined in the survey and low explained variance highlight the need for further research. Third, its convenience sampling approach restricted the generalizability of the findings.² Fourth, the COVID-19 pandemic could have shaped the responses through heightened awareness and sensitivity toward health topics. Fifth, it relied on school leaders' opinions without complementary qualitative data gathering efforts. Sixth, further comparative research can enhance understanding of how HP is shaped within countries' specific structural, cultural, and policy contexts. Such cross-national analyses can contribute to the development of contextually grounded theories and provide insights that can inform research and practice (Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

Conclusion

This study shows that school leaders' attitudes toward HP are context-dependent factors that influence HP implementation. Although school leadership is important in Malaysia and Switzerland, governing mechanisms and institutional arrangements shape its influence. In Malaysia, national guidelines and a distributed leadership model support consistent HP implementation. In Switzerland, outcomes depend more heavily on individual leaders' attitudes. These findings indicate that leadership, governance, and HP are intertwined and that simple policy transfer across systems is not recommended.

This study was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic—a period that heightened health concerns and stress-tested governance—and the findings suggest that crises can reinforce stabilizing state guidance (as in Malaysia) while amplifying local variability in decentralized systems (as in Switzerland). Further research is needed to examine school leaders' attitudes across education systems and the varying importance of other characteristics for HP implementation. In highly federal systems, where leaders have greater autonomy, attributes such as attitudes may be especially significant. Therefore, this study suggests that HP be integrated into school leader training. Leksy et al. (2024) found that HP is not systematically included in European school leader training and recommended ongoing competence development, a European competence framework for health-promoting leadership, and a monitoring system for HP programs.

To ensure the effective implementation of international HP standards, policy levers must align governance realities to achieve fidelity while maintaining contextual adaptations. For example, centralized systems benefit from clear standards and scaling mechanisms, whereas decentralized systems require leadership development, incentives, and networked coordination.

² The Swiss sample aligned with national school leader demographics (Tulowitzki et al., 2022)

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